

“It’s simple and practical!”: EFL learners’ views on learning strategies in essay writing

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This paper aims to uncover the types of strategies employed by high-achiever students in essay writing classes and discern the reasons for their exercise of those strategies. Ten students from the Department of English Language Education at one of the universities in Banda Aceh, Indonesia, were purposefully selected as participants. Interviews were used as the tool for data collection to gain information on the specific learning strategies employed by high achiever EFL learners in writing classes, and the motivations behind their adoption of the strategies. The findings revealed that memory and cognitive strategies (direct strategies) and metacognitive (indirect strategies) were favorably used by high-achieving students. The strategies were employed by students due to their simplicity, practicality, and effectiveness. The findings indicate that the strategies used by high achiever students are largely attributable to their uncomplicatedness and expediency rather than being multi-faceted and time-consuming.

Keywords: EFL Learners; Essay Writing; High Achiever; Learning Strategies; Metacognition

1. Introduction

The English language has four fundamental skills: speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Mastering these skills are essential in today’s globalized society. This approach has been particularly helpful in bridging the disparities concerning the concept and everyday use of English education for foreign language learners. One of those Basic English skills, writing, is measured equally as a central yet demanding ability. Writing is regarded as a productive skill in language learning (Jabali, 2018; Toba et al., 2019; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009a), where individuals generate linguistic production through composed

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text (Harmer, 2007). Writing is a critical academic skill that learners must acquire (Fareed et al., 2016).

To some extent, some individuals identify writing as congenial work, permitting them to express thoughts, concepts, and feelings through various means, making the most of their innate understanding (Yulianti & Fadhly, 2020). According to Brown (2007), writing is a way of interacting with arguments to express opinions, feelings, and insights. This suggests that individuals can develop preferences, retain remarkable resourcefulness, and prompt their thinking without limitation. However, some learners embrace diverse perceptions of writing. Certainly, many learners also vent their weariness during writing activities. This is partly because learners are not properly subjected to academic writing before they register as students at universities or higher education institutions. Even at universities, there is little instruction offered on academic writing, with only a few hours or semester credits dedicated to this objective. The situations encountered during writing practice may be due to several issues, ranging from inadequate vocabulary, restricted grammar understanding, lack of enthusiasm, and low self-confidence in writing (Muthalib et al., 2023; cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b, 2007c).

Writing involves a broad understanding of the subject matter, and the goal of the intended readership, including the language and its structural characteristics associated with grammar, spelling, and capitalization (Mertosono & Erniwati, 2023). Because writing requires specific skills from students, language learning strategies are important for addressing writing challenges. Winarto (2015) also specified that the use of learning strategies is an indispensable component of developing writing skills (Zuhairi & Umamah, 2016). Brown (2001) further referred to language learning strategies as particular methods employed by students to achieve success in their education (cf. Nemati et al., 2010). Consequently, the use of suitable approaches in learning development considerably alleviates learning-related problems (Yulianti & Fadhly, 2020). An effective learner, therefore, recognizes and uses language learning strategies that are applicable in their contexts.

Learning strategies allow learners to autonomously classify and recognize their learning inclinations and competences. EFL learners who retain cognizance of operational approaches for their ability development achieve extra achievement, in contrast to individuals with a lack of mastery of their tailored strategies. Learning strategies are typically categorized into two main types; direct and indirect learning strategies (O'Malley & Chamot, 1990). Direct strategies consist of several subtypes, including memory, cognitive, and compensation strategies, while indirect strategies include metacognitive, affective, and social strategies (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2010, 2014b).

A subject taught at the Department of English Language Education, Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh, Indonesia, is Essay Writing. EFL learners, in this course, must produce a brief essay on a certain topic. From our preliminary observations, we observed an uncommon relationship between EFL learners' skill level in this course and their academic accomplishments. Based on the recent summary of Essay Writing class marks at the Department of English Language Education, a substantial dissimilarity was detected between the EFL learners who scored the finest results and those who achieved ordinary marks in the class. Most EFL learners obtained B grades, while a minority obtained C grades instead of A-. Accordingly, it can be said that most EFL learners scored lower-middle range writing abilities. Roughly, simply 25% of EFL learners in the class received A- and A grades.

Although there is a growing corpus of work on successful learning strategies for Indonesian EFL learners, there is still a noticeable research gap concerning the viewpoints of high-achieving students in relation to writing classes, especially essay writing. While most prior research has heavily focused on the generic aspects of motivation (Diasti & Mbato, 2020), beliefs and performance (Rahmiati et al., 2019), or the four types of English skills (Atmowardoyo et al., 2021), the specific insights of high achiever students in essay writing classes, particularly in the setting of English for foreign language learners in Aceh, the northernmost province of Indonesia, remain largely unexplored. Therefore, in response to the aforementioned research gap, this study addressed the following research questions:

- (1) What learning strategies are used by high-achieving EFL learners in essay writing classes?
- (2) Why did high achiever EFL learners use these strategies in their essay writing classes?

2. Background

2.1. Writing

Hayes (1996) asserted that writing is a rational practice that involves understanding and emotion. This involves deliberate intellectual determination, which demands constant support over a long period. Writing, according to Emig (1977), is the active process of learning that results in dynamic texts that need mastery, including the application of orthography and punctuation, and words or language orchestration to constructively communicate and express intentions. Writing is imperative in that EFL learners must possess it because it improves their ability to participate in analytical reasoning (Al Mubarak, 2017; see also Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a, 2014a, 2023). Writing proficiency greatly improves social and academic

performance, as well as communication. In addition to its role in teaching, writing has a huge impact on the public lives of EFL learners, and above all in their future competence (Okpe & Onjewu, 2017). Attaining writing expertise enables EFL learners to successfully link their thinking and views to others through strong and logical written communication.

In addition to presenting stories, writing is a skill that allows the exploration of ideas and subjects (Goodall, 2018). When writing is executed proficiently, it effectively links thoughts, psychological states, and emotions, as it demands both effort and motivation. The word "effort" denotes particular manners and performances involved in EFL learning. Writing is a refined practice that empowers authors to examine concepts and considerations in a discernible way. Writing encompasses numerous aspects, including content, vocabulary, language usage, conventions, and writing processes (Weigle, 2002).

According to Harmer (2007), the writing process contains four distinctive phases: planning, drafting, editing, and the final version (cf. Birjandi et al. 2004). Planning is a fundamental phase in which the author cautiously opts for, and manages, concepts for writing composition, in view of the envisioned goal and target addressees, which eventually inspire the selection of genre and structure. Planning is the initial phase in which EFL learners place and anticipate their understanding. Van den Bergh et al. (2016) also labeled this phase as "formulating", as it enables learners to discover and produce various thoughts through courses of devising, topic breakdown, and planning.

The second stage is drafting, during which learners consolidate their opinions and decide the organization of their writing. Faraj (2015) argued that drafting also involves *scaffolding* (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016) students' writing because it helps provide the overall arrangement of writing. Drafting is the primary phase in which the author begins the piece of writing, articulating his/her thinking and providing supplementary information in the form of a first draft. The key objective is to write down the arguments on paper, without feeling any *anxiety* (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2015) concerning precision, sentence structure, standards, organization, spelling, and other interrelated features—basically, writing out the content engendered during the pre-writing phase. During the drafting phase, learners naturally search for feedback from their peers or lecturers to detect and rectify any inaccuracies that may have occurred during the writing practice (Harmer, 2007).

The following phase is editing, which is repeatedly denoted as adjusting or reviewing (Hyland, 2019). Once feedback or responses are received from other parties regarding basic improvements in writing, the review course is initiated. Learners who lack external feedback on their writing are normally involved in the practice of rereading and reviewing their work. Those with good writing skills participate in the practice of meticulously rereading, reexamining, and

revising their written works many times until they reach precision and comprehension. During the review practice, learners analytically scrutinize their writing to decide whether their intended meaning has been efficiently and precisely communicated. At this point, the emblematic procedure involves reexamining the writing, rearranging it, integrating supplementary content, and increasing the clarity of the writing. In the final version phase, the authors apply the required alterations and make their definite version. Moreover, the final version requires many other elements that must be considered to provide an excellent piece of work, including grammar, idiomatic expressions, and punctuation.

2.2. Essay writing

In university contexts, there are countless forms of writing, including essay writing, which is a type of academic writing. Primarily, the achievement of devising excellent essay writing is considered a method to achieve excellent academic writing (Day, 2023). Van Geyte (2013) also asserted that essay writing remains one of the most popular forms of assignments.

An essay is a succinct and carved arrangement that offers the author a precise standpoint on a definite subject, to be assessed or measured. While learners can produce writing conceptions, only a restricted number of learners retain the ability to successfully create essays. The goal of this writing form is to convey ideas on convincing themes and encourage learners to deliver a complete and reflective examination of the topic. According to Oshima and Hogue (2006), essays are carved works that contain many long passages and focus on particular topics. Due to the extensive dimensions of essays, it is vital to find a methodical construction and develop it in advance before starting the writing practice with an outline.

Essays can be categorized into four diverse groups: (a) argumentative, (b) expository, (c) narrative, and (d) descriptive essays (Collins et al., 2021; Marue & Pantas, 2019; Noroozi et al., 2016; Rabab'ah et al., 2022). Argumentative and expository essays mainly emphasize providing accurate evidence and explicating numerous thoughts; narrative and descriptive essays encompass the use of resourcefulness and the arrangement of attractive writing.

2.3. Learning strategies

Many scholars have communicated concepts linked to the taxonomy of writing approaches. Ideas for writing strategies result from the standard of learning strategies. The basis for accepting this notion is that writing plays a key role in language learning, which aims to improve learners' understanding and expertise in several capacities, such as reading, listening, and speaking. Thus, various researchers have consigned substantial importance to the idea of

writing-related learning practices (Gafoordeen, 2013; Zuhairi & Umamah, 2016).

The practice of classifying and grouping language learning strategies was used to inspect and discuss approaches associated with writing in detail. The grouping includes two major clusters: (a) direct strategies, and (b) indirect strategies. As Nemati et al. (2010) have indicated, direct strategies involve direct engagement with a foreign language, whereas indirect strategies accelerate language learning without direct use of the target language.

Direct strategies include memory, cognitive, and compensation strategies. The memory strategy helps students retain and memorize detailed evidence. As considered by Goundar (2015), and Vogel and Schwabe (2016), memory strategies can be classified into three groups: (a) mechanical techniques, (b) structuring review, and (c) implanting new vocabulary. Memory strategies help learners form links between ideas or objects in the second language and one another while discounting the conception process. Likewise, these strategies include the use of reasoning procedures to obtain and recall fresh information and awareness in memory, as well as to recover it when necessary. Varied memory-related strategies do exist, some of which exploit methodical series (e.g., acronyms) aimed at simplifying information repossession and learning, while others highlight the use of sounds (e.g., rhyming words) aimed at easing learning and recovery.

Cognitive strategy is an approach that allows learners to relate to the information through conceptual handling, such as grouping matters or taking notes of decisive evidence for imminent recall. Cognitive strategies are those that require the transformation, production, or inquiry of learning resources (Ellis, 2015). Additionally, problem-solving approaches are a common component of cognitive strategies in EFL, and they motivate students to examine linguistic patterns and use critical thinking when faced with language difficulties. Teachers can enable EFL students to actively interact with language resources, improve their comprehension, and eventually enable a more successful and independent language learning process by supporting cognitive methods.

An additional direct strategy is the compensation strategy. This strategy helps learners disable knowledge boundaries that hinder their ability to understand and create the target language. This method is central for both producing the target language successfully and reimbursing any knowledge breach. This strategy is valuable and helpful in nurturing and increasing learners' enthusiasm and competence to attain expertise in the target language. This corresponds to the one piloted by Maharani et al. (2018), who found that compensation seemed to be the major approach among learners who created

poor writing, whereas it became the most well-known or often used strategy among learners who produced excellent writing.

In addition, indirect strategies consist of three types: (a) metacognitive, (b) affective, and (c) social. The metacognitive strategy mainly facilitates learning management. The strategy revolves around centering, arranging, planning, and evaluating learning (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2008). The second indirect strategy is the affective strategy with three key elements: (a) lowering one's anxiety, (b) encouraging oneself, and (c) taking one's emotional temperature (Oxford, 2017; cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2011, 2015). The subsequent components—motivation, positive attitudes, and emotions—are also central to helping learners (MacIntyre & Vincze, 2017). Language learners are equipped with the skills to control their feelings and emotions while advancing in a personalized learning mode. Learners will encounter an indirect increase in motivation and a shrinking apprehension following the use of these particular strategies. Affective strategies are, in short, related to motivation, attitudes, and emotions.

The last type of indirect strategy is the social strategy. Despite being categorized as an indirect strategy, Kendal et al. (2018) asserted that social strategies deliver considerable benefits to education despite their indirect involvement. By integrating a social strategy, learners can openly assess their own learning and ensure the degree to which they see themselves as having power over the learning situation.

2.4. High achiever

The expressions "gifted" and "achiever" are occasionally used reciprocally in theoretical works to designate persons with excellent academic achievement compared to their classmates. Zohar et al. (2001) entitle high achiever learners to be stereotypically called characters with brilliant academic talent, as many scholars have confirmed. The word "high achiever" was used to represent learners who shine in their academic competences, plus having extraordinary notch and emerging modified and well-organized methods to improve their learning practices and achieve better accomplishment (Putri & Wahyuni, 2019).

High achievers obtain outstanding marks and achieve educational achievement. Normally, they establish robust talent in a timely organization to consolidate and complete their responsibilities. A dependable way to identify high-achiever learners is by assessing their GPA (grade point average). Dooley et al. (2012) claimed that students who maintain an average of 90% completion, or greater, in their top six courses are considered high achiever students.

High achiever learners possess numerous inimitable characteristics. They are categorized as focused learners who enthusiastically think about teaching. They actively participate in discussions by making pioneering intellectual contributions, providing systematic responses to multifaceted subjects, and articulating strong attention and knowledgeable views. Burrow et al. (2012) pinpointed that high-achieving learners hold marks that exceed the regular. Learners who produce exceptional scores do so due to exercising better determination and enjoying greater aptitudes in comparison to their peers.

The current study examines the learning strategies utilized by high-achieving EFL learners from the Department of English Language Education at Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry, who achieved top scores in the essay writing class.

3. Method

A qualitative research design, chosen to align with the research questions, was employed in this study. Qualitative research is often used to explore the significance of fundamental concepts and investigate themes, offering nuanced insights into social phenomena (Creswell, 2012). A framework was used to deepen the outcomes of the study based on the analysis of the participants' interview responses.

3.1. Participants

The selection of EFL learners was based on their performance in the essay writing course conducted during the most recent semester. This approach allows for an evaluation of their understanding of the course material. A purposive sampling procedure was employed to select participants. According to Bryman (2012), purposive sampling intentionally selects individuals, institutions, documents, and other elements directly related to the research issue. This method focuses on choosing cases that provide high-quality data and are directly relevant to the outcomes of the study (cf. Patton, 2002).

In addition, a homogenous sampling method was used. A homogenous purposive sample is chosen based on specific characteristics or features that are uniform among participants (Holloway & Wheeler, 1996; Patton, 2002). Participants were selected from six Essay Writing courses, with a total population of 180 undergraduates. The final sample consisted of 10 students who achieved high marks on essay writing. Selection criteria included:

- Completion of the essay writing course
- A score of A or above 90 in the essay writing class
- Enrollment as student in the Department of English Language Education

3.2. Procedure

Interviews were used as the primary method of data collection to obtain detailed information about the participants' ideas, knowledge, opinions, beliefs, and emotions regarding the selected issues. Responses from these interviews were recorded (cf. Creswell, 2012). This study employed semi-structured interviews, which are characterized by their flexible and informal nature. The purpose of these interviews, à la Diccico-Bloom and Crabtree (2006), is to gain a deep understanding of the topic through project-specific and open-ended questions. Semi-structured interviews also involve pre-determined questions but allow for additional probing to elicit more comprehensive responses from participants (Stuckey, 2013). This method offers adaptability, as interviews can be conducted either individually or in a group setting. For this study, individual interviews were preferred over focus group discussions. Each interview lasted between 30 to 40 minutes.

The interview questions were divided into two sections: (a) five questions addressed the first research question (R1), which focused on identifying the specific learning strategies used by high-achieving EFL learners in writing classes; and (b) five questions addressed the second research question (R2), which explored the motivations behind their use of these strategies.

3.3. Data Analysis

The participant interview data were recorded using a narrative refinement procedure. The data were then coded and organized within a conceptual framework. This process involved categorizing the data into distinct themes and patterns (cf. Habiburrahim et al., 2021). The interview data were subjected to thematic analysis through a systematic coding method. Broad themes were identified and further broken down into more detailed categories. These categories specifically pertain to EFL learners in the Writing Class who achieved A grades, corresponding to a score range of 90–100.

4. Results

The data gathered from the interviews revealed that students lacked a clear understanding of the specific methods they employed. They were primarily focused on the three distinct stages of writing—pre-writing, drafting, and rewriting—as suggested by their lecturers. According to most of the students, they did not have a well-defined writing plan. Observing and emulating the writing styles of others led them to adopt similar approaches. Many of the students believed that consistent practice is the most effective way to improve their writing skills. Additionally, the results indicated that EFL learners predominantly use a metacognitive approach when assessing their writing

assignments. Writing and planning were closely linked tasks, followed by drafting and editing.

According to the results, high achiever EFL learners used more direct strategies than indirect ones in essay writing exercises intended to answer the first research problem. The results also suggested that high-achieving EFL learners used these strategies because their writing performance improved, which addressed the second research question. Two main themes emerge from the use of such strategies: (a) simplicity, and (b) efficiency.

A direct strategy is one in which the target language is fully utilized in the learning process. Direct strategies assist language handling in the brain. The three groups of direct strategies are (a) memory, (b) cognitive, and (c) compensatory strategies—each of which distinctively performs linguistic control and functions as an individual goal. As our data revealed, the participants applied these strategies to their writing tasks.

The first strategy is the memory strategy, which retrieves information from long-term memory when the need for communication increases. Memory strategy accelerates the recollection of urgent evidence that students have encountered in written or spoken resources in a foreign language. Moreover, it helps in the retrieval of evidence from memory for understanding or idea construction. Here are some of the points made by the interviewees:

The finest approach to developing better at writing is to read more. I have faith that the more we read, the more familiar we will be to practice correct word selection and grammar. I rehearse writing using this method to get used to it, and it is stress-free. (P2)

Whenever I read something written in English, I get accustomed to it. It will be easier for you to track if you are familiar with reading scientific articles or journals in English. (P7)

The second direct strategy used by the participant was the cognitive strategy. Cognitive strategies consider four arrays of strategies: (a) receiving and sending messages (receiving concepts promptly and with information); (b) analyzing and reasoning (conveying and accurately functioning with writing and sound activities, identifying and using constructions and forms, recombining, and performing naturally); (c) converting and transmitting; and (d) creating advanced grammars for response and construction.

I like writing, and I often do it at home. I can simply complete the writing projects that my professor taught me. I plan to expand my lexis and read more. Vocabulary is essential because it is harder to place thoughts down in writing when we don't have it. Everybody composes in a diverse

manner, in my opinion, but the top strategy is exercise. In various circumstances, including mine, the learning concept alone is not enough. Like writing, the most operational tactic is to drill as much as you can when you have time. (P4)

Writing properly is an expertise I am constantly learning. Perhaps, once it derives to approach, repetition creates the finest solution. Each time I get the opportunity, I continually write and ask my professors for feedback on my writing. I think it is simpler to write sometimes because of this routine. (P6)

The compensation strategy is the last direct strategy. Regardless of knowledge constraints, this strategy allows learners to use original semantics for knowledge or construction. Through the application of a compensation strategy, such as using synonyms and prediction, EFL learners can impart their points to their interlocutors even though there is a major disparity in their own awareness. This strategy aims to disguise their grammar, proficiency, and vocabulary constraints.

In my opinion, writing involves placing every English expression together with appropriate phrasing and language rules. Accordingly, I improved my sentence structure and improved my vocabulary. If we are good at syntax and have an adequate vocabulary, writing will be much simpler and more concentrated. (P5)

The findings of the data analysis also indicated that the participants applied indirect strategies. Their statements provide insight into the indirect strategies they used. After a thorough analysis of the data, it was found that top achievers also used indirect strategies as an essential part of their academic toolset. The results highlighted the role indirect techniques play in high-achieving students' academic success and offer directions for educational interventions that support the overall student-success support system.

The metacognitive strategy was the first indirect strategy that the participants used. This approach empowers individuals to regulate their thinking (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2008). Metacognitive strategies comprise several strategies: (a) learning centering (reviewing and relating to acknowledged facts, giving attention, and postponing speech production to concentrate on listening); (b) learning organization and planning (gathering information about language learning, organizing, and establishing objectives and goals); and (c) learning evaluation (monitor and self-evaluate).

I follow my lecturer's instructions in writing class and do not use any particular writing strategies. I will adhere to the planning, drafting, and

revising processes. I believe thorough planning and preparation are the foundation of successful writing. I also often train myself by reading various scholarly works, which is a great way to gain new perspectives on various subjects. (P1)

I like writing, and my writing plan is to write every time I have the opportunity. I compose for a wide range of subjects. I also often read a lot of writing, which benefits me in knowing exactly how other people create thoughts in their writings. I ponder the greatest technique to upturn my composition's importance and skill is exercise. I regularly look for writing assistance and advice from Google and YouTube. In addition, enjoying it is central to success. I love to compose and teach it, so I'm assured I can achieve good results. (P3)

The participants further stated that they employed the affective strategy. Affective strategies empower learners to control their stimuli, approaches, and emotional states related to their knowledge of a foreign language. These basics are related to the control of learners who practice operational strategies. Emotional acumen is surrounded by paramount reasons for defining the success or disappointment of EFL learners. Knowledgeable EFL learners can adjust their feelings and approaches to the education process. One participant applies this individual strategy.

I'm constantly refining my writing skills. I trust that writing well is a result of a constructive approach; therefore, I continually try to develop my efforts and write more often. I typically compose when I get the opportunity, and I regularly receive comments on my writing from my professors. This practice has made it easier for me to write frequently. (P6)

In addition, the participants practiced social strategies to create worthy excellence in writing. This strategy stimulates interaction with others, generally in discourse contexts. The reputation of this strategy originates from the information that language characterizes a method of social exchange (Salmani Nodoushan, 2024); it is over which individual discussions occur. The following examples are what the participants in the data interview indicated:

To confer my writing, I always seek groups. Writing together with groups widens my outlook on what constitutes good writing composition. Individuals near me give me categorically encouraging comments. (P1)

In my spare time, I refer my friends for help and consult my professors about the excellence of my efforts. My groups and I often start conversation groups to cheer and oversee one other's writing. (P5)

As the EFL learners stated, the strategies they employed were unintuitive to practice. As the learners indicated, the goal of a strategy is to accelerate the finishing of an assignment by providing greater organization and target. The aim is to offer assistance to printing resources. In the absence of such direction, a writing arrangement may only appear unsystematic, disjointed, and possibly counterproductive.

This is a method that I believe is fairly easy to practice while writing. (P3)

This is an available and truly convenient plan for me. In my opinion, a changed approach will not really help me write better. However, once I use these techniques, writing happens more logically to me. (P5)

Many participants informed us that they employed particular writing strategies because of their operational characteristics and practical application. Learners stated that engaging in these strategies enhanced their self-assurance in writing. Effective strategies exploit distributed resources in line with the prescribed plan and yield preferred results.

Writing using this strategy provides me with the logic of self-reliance and comfort. In addition to improving my final scores, the method has been relatively valuable in facilitating my ability to write better. (P2)

Using this method has equally improved the excellence of my writing and my writing mark. I must read a lot of references before practicing them when I am writing. This method is incredible and works well for increasing confidence and viewpoint when writing. (P5)

5. Discussion

In this section, the emphasis is on interpreting and contextualizing the research findings into more understandable writing instruction in classroom settings. This discussion aims to illuminate how simplicity and practicality emerge as central themes in high-achieving students' preferred learning strategies through careful analysis of the identified themes and patterns. Additionally, it explores how educators can apply these insights to improve writing instruction and meet the unique needs of academically proficient students.

The first research inquiry centered around the type of strategy employed by learners in their writing to gain a greater score. Based on the interviews, one important result was the recurring importance that students attached to 'memory strategy'. It can be argued that consistent reading and archiving of data acquired from several sources is favorable for high achiever learners. According to the learners, the practice of breeding concepts turns out to be unproblematic when they refer to various references. This supports the idea

proposed by Rashtchi and Porkar (2020) that memory strategies can enable learners to establish cognitive memories with present information through pre-writing brainstorming, particularly in argumentative essay writing. The results also indicate how important the review strategy is (cf. Cargill & O'Connor, 2021), exclusively for learners who prefer concrete writing methods. When learners encounter problems, they might improve their consideration by reviewing their written projects.

Additionally, the findings indicated that learners practice cognitive means. A crucial characteristic of these strategies is their capacity to influence learners or change the target language (Hardan, 2013). This strategy includes mental practices that openly activate inbound data (Pongsukvajchakul, 2021). For them, this strategy is very helpful because of its weight on exercise, which is one of its most central facets in writing. Learners agree that consistent training is the most operational routine to increase the quality of their writing. This is in line with the study conducted by Arnold et al. (2017), which suggested that understanding individual differences and task formulation within the framework of cognitive aspects can help students find more effective learning strategies. Furthermore, high-achieving students frequently use cognitive methods when writing essays. For EFL students, the capacity to generate ideas, draw conclusions, and draw inspiration from personal experiences is essential to the composition of their work. Lecturers can take advantage of this by engaging those activities in essay writing to help students perform better (Bean & Melzer, 2021).

The second research question addressed the causes of the engagement of strategies by high-achieving EFL learners in the essay writing class. Two important answers from the interviews were elicited. One reason is that learners recognize the use of these strategies as being simple. This sides with the observation made by Newman (1994) that self-regulated (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2012) and high achiever learners' performance is equitably caused by their adaptive help-seeking, and simple and rational repertoires. The results of this study also specify high achiever students in terms of the approachability and naturalness of their preferred strategies. This implies that, as the complexity of essay writing assignments increases, so does the ability of high-achiever students to facilitate cognitive processing by employing different workable and practical learning strategies (Seli, 2019).

Another argument is that the strategies are highly operational and can encourage students to write. The term "affective", in 'affective strategies', encompasses emotions, viewpoints, incentives, and issues (Rustam et al., 2015). Adopting applicable writing strategies will yield numerous advantages. This was emphasized in the interviews where participants stated that the technique was highly beneficial and successful in enhancing their writing

abilities and academic performance. In this sense, high-achieving students recognize the importance of both quality and quantity in learning. They admitted that they understood more and scored more after using particular learning strategies. Therefore, the strategic use of high-achievers' learning strategies may have a significant impact on overall academic performance of students (Hattie & Donoghue, 2016).

An effective learning strategy is one that (a) efficiently uses the provided resources in accordance with the plans and (b) achieves the desired outcomes. Individuals need to consistently assess their application and effectiveness to determine whether their strategy successfully achieves the targeted objective. In the context of this study, the efficacy of the chosen learning strategies can be measured by their impact on academic success—i.e., their washback (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b, 2021). High achiever students' use of effective learning strategies is expected to demonstrate (a) their proficiency in understanding the subject matter and (b) their capability to showcase their knowledge in evaluations and examinations. In the words of Nisbet and Shucksmith (2017), this may well serve as a mediating pathway to improve students' academic outcomes.

6. Conclusion

This study has provided insights into the perceptions of high achiever EFL learners of their preferred learning strategies in essay writing classes. The findings revealed that memory and cognitive strategies (direct strategies) and metacognitive (indirect strategies) were favorably used by high-achieving students in writing classes. The strategies were employed by students due to their simplicity, practicality, and effectiveness. The findings indicate that the strategies used by high achiever students are largely attributable to their uncomplicatedness and expediency rather than being multi-faceted and time-consuming.

It is imperative to remind the reader of the limitations of the study that might have an impact on how the outcomes are understood and how relevant they are. The study, in its actuality, mainly focused on high-achiever learners who may not represent the larger EFL learner population in writing classes. Their feelings may vary profoundly from those of ordinary or striving EFL learners, restraining the generalizability of the conclusions to a broader population. Furthermore, the EFL learning strategies preferred by high-achieving EFL learners in one situation may not necessarily relate to other didactic settings or classes with diverse context-specific applicability.

The implications of this study include both didactic exercise and further investigation in the field of writing education where uncomplicatedness and pragmatism in teaching, particularly in the area of English language education,

may lead to better learner involvement and diversity of learning strategies. Hence, extensive research and further case studies may reveal if high achiever learners' accomplishments might inform the specialized growth of diverse learner populations.

Author's Statement

All authors confirm that they collaboratively discussed and developed the concept for this paper. The first author proposed the initial idea and managed data collection, whereas the second, third, fourth, and fifth authors were instrumental in the overall conceptualization, editing, and refinement of the article.

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